

Development and Evaluation of Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guidelines

Mary Wilson DNP, CRNA - Margaret Brady PhD, RN, CPNP-PC - Michael Boytim EdD, CRNA

Background

- Poor dentition is linked to below average academic performance, maladjusted psychosocial behavior, and overall decreased physical health in school aged children.
- For children requiring multiple dental procedures and those who are uncooperative or anxious, sedation and general anesthesia may be necessary.
- Patient safety and the administration of anesthesia with cautious oversight among this population can be challenging.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of the project was to develop evidence-based pediatric dental anesthesia clinical practice guidelines for an ambulatory surgery center.

Method

- An expert panel (Delphi method) was recruited to participate in the development and evaluation of pediatric dental anesthesia outpatient guidelines.
- The expert panel participated in three rounds of review and revision of the guidelines using the Delphi method until 100% consensus was reached in the 3rd round

Framework

Implementation

- Dissemination of the PDAGs occurred at the primary researcher's state professional organization.
- Anesthesia providers within the state have contacted the researcher regarding the implementation of the guidelines.
- Second phase of research will be continued utilizing the PDSA model for implementation and dissemination of the Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guidelines.

Discussion

- Evidence-based research supports improvement in clinical practice with the use of safety guidelines when administering anesthesia to pediatric patients (AAP, 2016).
- Using a standardized guideline such as the PDAG in practice settings is necessary to provide quality care to this vulnerable population.

Conclusion

The evidence supports the formalized development and implementation of standardized guidelines as a credible method for reducing morbidity and mortality associated with anesthesia in the outpatient pediatric dental setting. Pediatric anesthesia dental guidelines are necessary to decrease mortality and morbidity in this vulnerable population.

Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guidelines

